

Promotion and Brand Image of Vespa Motorcycle: Customer Perspective

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Abstract:- The aim of this research is to investigate how promotion and brand image impact purchasing decisions for Vespa motorcycle in Malang, East Java, Indonesia. This study used quantitative approach. A total of 100 Vespa users are as respondents of this study. There are two independent factors in this study: promotion (X1) and brand image (X2), along with one dependent variable, purchasing decisions (Y). Multiple linear regression analysis is applied as an analytical method after conducting the classical assumption analyses of normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) as an analytical tool. It can be inferred from the study of several linear regression analysis tests when combined, it can be seen that both simultaneously and partially the results of this study indicate that promotion and brand image have a significant effect on purchasing decisions for VESPA.

Keyword:- Promotion, Brand Image, Purchasing decisions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tight business competition now requires every company must have innovation and creativity in designing marketing strategies so that the company can strengthen the company's position, get profit, maintain viability and develop the company in the face of competition (Khasanah, 2011). Marketing strategies that can be carried out by companies to face business competition is through promotional activities and highlight the brand image owned by the company (Wijaya, 2013). Recently, the company is faced with a fairly large population growth rapidly and diverse human activities, so that everyone want all these activities to be done quickly.

Therefore, the need for transportation has become a basic human need which is where humans prefer personal transportation, especially motorcycles compared to public transportation, to support daily activities.

Indonesia is one of the countries where the automotive business growing rapidly so that the value of demand also increases because people tend to prefer private vehicles, especially motorcycle. Various kinds and types of motorcycles faced by consumers today become a challenge for motorcycle manufacturers so that it requires more creative and innovative in reaching or fulfilling desires the consumer. Vespa is one of the motor vehicle products from Italian company PIAGGIO which is a company in Indonesia with the name of PT Piaggio Indonesia. In Indonesia, Vespa is quite famous among olds and young people, so that the brand image of the company is running well enough, that way the company can carry out various kinds of innovations

to provide new things that can enjoyed for Vespa motorcycle lovers.

The consumer must make decisions about where to buy, what brand to buy, what model to buy, how much to buy, when to buy, how much money to spend, and how to pay. Marketers can impact these judgments by giving information about their products or services that can help consumers make better selections. A marketer's job is to concentrate on the entire purchasing process rather than merely on a purchase decision, because customers go through several stages before making a decision (Basil et al., 2013). Understanding buyer behavior is difficult because a variety of factors might influence a customer's decision to buy. Consumers may spend less time considering whether to buy low- or high-value products in some circumstances because they believe that meeting their requirements is more essential. As a result, marketing managers have been asked to implement techniques that encourage consumers to buy their products by developing an effective marketing strategy.

Several research found that promotion and brand image influenced purchasing intention directly or indirectly. Rizwan&Husam (2021) found that brand equity has a considerable beneficial impact on the purchase intention of health takaful clients in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and that all three dimensions of brand equity contribute significantly to overall brand equity. Age, income, and religion do not attenuate the link between brand equity and purchase intention, according to the findings. Related with personal factors and sales promotion, Rehman et al. (2017) found that personal characteristics and sub-dimensions such as market savvy, stability, and open-mindedness have been shown to have a favorable impact on purchasing behavior. Sales promotion, as well as its sub-dimensions such as social aspects and physical layout, have good effects. The impact of sales promotions on brand choice behavior is demonstrated by Alvarez &Vázquez(2005), then establishments want to sway consumers' purchasing decisions. TeckWeng& Cyril (2013) found that consumers' choices for sales promotion techniques will have an impact on their buy intent and satisfaction for all products. Personal value, on the other hand, has no substantial impact on consumers' purchase satisfaction or behavior intention for any product. Based on the results of those research, this study aims to determine the effect of promotion and brand image on the decision to buy a Vespa motorcycle.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Promotion

According to Kotler & Keller (2012), marketing is an activity identify and meet consumer or human needs and social. A summary of the definition of marketing is meeting needs consumers in a profitable way. Hasan (2014) and Nasution et al. (2019) stated that promotion is the process of communicating the marketing mix variables that organizations must use to advertise their products. Managing a marketing communication system necessitates an effective and efficient design strategy as well as sales initiatives. There are several indicators of promotion. Those indicators are advertising, sales promotion, public relations and publicity, personal selling, and direct marketing.

Sianturi et al. (2019) found that promotion had positive and significant impact on costumers' repurchase decision. Karwur (2016) conducted research at IndomaretPaniki on the impact of retail marketing mix on purchasing decisions. The findings revealed that the retail marketing mix, which includes products, prices, promotions, services, store design, shop location, and store atmosphere, has a significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions. Products, prices, and promotions had a major impact on the decision to repurchase Kalimilk milk products in Yogyakarta. In the service company, Putra et al. (2020) investigate the effect of marketing mix on purchase decision. The results show that in the hotel, consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by hotel's products; prices are also influence the consumer purchasing decisions. There is also the hotel's location has an impact on the purchase choice. The study also found that the hotel's promotion has an impact on the consumer's purchase choice. Santoso& Audi (2021) analyze product quality, brand image, promotion and product knowledge on the purchasing decisions. Using 96 respondents, the study found that consumer confidence, consumer experience and sales promotion had a positive and significant impact on purchasing decisions.

B. Brand Image

According to Tjijtonoand Diana (2015) a brand is a sign in the form of words, pictures, names, letters, numbers, color arrangements, or a combination of the whole that has distinguishing power and is used in trade in goods or services. Meanwhile, according to Kotler and Keller (2012) brand image is the name, term, a symbol, sign, design, or a combination of these, for the purpose of to identify the goods or services of a person or group seller and serve as a differentiator from competitors' goods and services. Miati (2020) describes brand image as a set of associations that people have with a particular brand. If a brand's relationship is built on experience and a variety of data, it will be stronger. As a vital aspect of brand equity, brand image represents a brand's worth to its customers. Any object that may be classified as an image might cause a person to have diverse beliefs, impressions, and ideas. When a set of associations is important to customers, it might be viewed as a brand image. Brand image also refers to any image of a product in the consumer's mind that is associated with a specific brand (Aaker, 2010).

Perera et al. (2019) and Dissabandara (2020) found that brand equity had a significant impact on customer purchase intension in their investigations. Similarly, Adam & Akber (2016) concluded that when a client chooses one brand over another despite the availability of additional features in alternate brands, it is merely the product of brand equity. As a result, commercial firms and marketers should prioritize brand equity in order to increase market share and profit. According to Kotler & Keller (2012), indicators of brand image are strength of brand association, favorability of brand association, and uniqueness of brand association.

C. Purchasing Decision

Kotler and Armstrong (2018) define that purchasing decisions are part of consumer behavior, namely the study of about how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, use and how goods, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy their needs and wants. Purchasing decision is a process of evaluating and selecting from various alternatives in accordance with certain interests with determine the option that is considered the most profitable. Marketing researchers Kotler and Keller (2012) devised a "five-stage model" of the purchasing decision process, which includes problem definition, information search, alternative evaluation, purchase decision, and post-purchase behavior.

Santoso& Cahyadi (2014) and Ruangkanjanases et al. (2020) stated that existing clients and new consumers have different perspectives on purchase intension. The purchase intension of new consumer reveals customer interest, choice, and overall behavior, whereas the PI of established customers predicts customer trust, contentment, and the likelihood of future purchases. Marketers are usually curious about the aspects that influence a customer's purchase intension. They may lead their clients to a specific brand by recognizing these variables, which is the goal of all marketers (Tariq et al., 2017). According to Kotler (2004), there are three indicators in determining decisions purchases are: stability in a product, habit in buying a product, and speed in buying a product.

D. Research Method

Population of this study is the users of Vespa motorcycle in Malang, East Java, Indonesia. Using accidental sampling, this study has 100 respondents. Data was collected through self-administered questionnaires distributed by the researcher. There are three variables for this study that consists of purchasing decision as dependent variable, promotion and brand image as independent variables. Each variable has six item in questionnaires. This study also examines the validity and reliability of the questionnaires. Validity test is used to measure whether the questionnaire is valid or not. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the question items are able to reveal something to be measured by the questionnaire. Decision making is based on the P-Value value or its significance where if the significance value obtained is less than 0.05 then the item or question is declared valid. Based on the validity test conducted on promotion, brand image and purchasing decisions of the overall indicators on each variable, the significance value is much smaller than 0.05. While the value of the correlation coefficient produced by each indicator is greater than r table.

This shows that each variable indicator is declared valid. Reliability testing in this study uses the Alpha formula. Statistical results shows that all variables have a fairly large Alpha coefficient, which is above 0.60 or it can be said that all indicators of each variable from the questionnaire are reliable. So that the items in each of these variables are suitable to be used as a measuring tool.

This study used multiple linear regression to analyze the influence of promotion and brand image on purchasing decision. Classical assumptions also used in this study in order to have Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE) which means that regression model doesn't have problems. The classical assumptions that used in this study are normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Respondent Description

Based on the responds of the questionnaires that distributed to 100 respondents who users of Vespa motorcycle in Malang, East Java, Indonesia, it can be described the characteristics of the respondents based on gender, income, job, and age. Based on the gender, the respondents of this study consists of 81 (81%) male and 19 (19%) female. Based on the income, there are 11% that have income between 1.5 million and 2 million, 74% between 2 million and 4 million, 13% between 4 million and 6 million, and only 2% above 6 million. It can be concluded that majority users of Vespas have income between 2 million and 4 million. It can be said that the income owned by the respondent provides support in making purchases and maintenance of the existence of a VESPA brand motor vehicle. Statistical analysis showed that 14% of the respondents are students of higher education, 10% are civil employees, 28% are private employees, and 48% are entrepreneurs. It can be seen that most of the respondents are entrepreneurs as much as 48 or 48%. This condition proves that the respondent's work supports the product purchase process, including purchasing the VESPA brand motor vehicle. Finally, based on ages, 15% of the respondents are between 17 and 19 years old, 26% are between 20 and 25 years old, 45% are between 26 and 30 years old, and 14% are above 30 years old. Based on the age, most of respondents are 26 until 30 years old, this age group is an age group that has high activity or productive age so that the existence of a motorbike can support the activities carried out.

B. Variable Description

The analysis of the answers per variable aims to find out a descriptive picture of the respondents in this study. In this study using descriptive statistical analysis techniques that describe respondents to the items asked questions. By using this basis, it can be seen the respondent's perception of the variables used in this study. Variable promotion in this study has six indicators that consists of advertisement in mass media, getting information about Vespa, massive promotion, getting information from internet, promotion about advantages being user of Vespa, and responds about who promote the Vespa. Respondents' responses regarding the advertisement for the VESPA S product in mass media

such as television, radio, and the internet are in accordance with the fact that most of them, namely 70 respondents or 70%, agreed and obtained a total score of 4.19 which was included in the very criteria agree. Only 1% who didn't agree about it.

Respondents' responses regarding having received notifications about the VESPA product in the form of emails and leaflets (pamphlets) and others showed that most of them, namely 63 respondents or 63% agreed and obtained a total score of 4.11 who entered in the criteria agree and only 2% who didn't agree about it. Respondents' responses to the VESPA sales promotion carried out massively and large shows that most of the 60 respondents or 60% agreed and obtained a total score of 4.06 which was included in the agreed criteria. No respondent is strongly disagree about this statement. Respondents' responses regarding having received notifications about the VESPA product from internet, namely 69 respondents or 69% agreed and obtained a total score of 4.11 who entered in the criteria strongly agree. In this case, no respondent who didn't agree and strongly didn't agree about this statement. Respondents' responses regarding the VESPA promotion further convinced me that the product was useful, indicating that most of the respondents, namely 58 respondents or 58%, agreed that the VESPA promotion further convinced me that the product was useful, obtaining a total score of 4.03 which is included in the agreed criteria. Finally, respondents' responses regarding the VESPA promotions were very creative, showing that most of them as many as 58 respondents or 58% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.98 which was included in the agreed criteria.

Brand image variable in this study has six indicators. Those indicators are uniqueness of Vespa, easiness of remembering the name of Vespa, the attractiveness in riding the Vespa, the famous of Vespa, interesting design, and the Vespa make feel confidence for people who ride it. Based on the questionnaires that distributed to the respondents, respondents' responses about having heard/seen that the VESPA has a unique and futuristic design indicate that most of the 57 respondents or 57% agree that they have heard/seen that the VESPA has a unique and futuristic design. Respondents' responses to the VESPA as an easy-to-remember brand showed that most of them, as many as 58 respondents or 58%, stated strongly agree and obtained a total score of 3.80 which was included in the criteria for strongly agree. Respondents' responses regarding having heard/seen that the VESPA has agile and comfortable handling when driving indicate that most of them agree that as many as 77 respondents or 77% agree with an average value of 3.98 which falls into the category strongly agree.

Respondents gave an assessment of the statement that VESPA is a big and well-known brand, indicating that most of it, as many as 70 respondents or 70% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.90 which was included in the criteria for strongly agree. Respondents gave an assessment of the statement regarding the VESPA having a more attractive design than other similar motorbikes, indicating that most of them, namely 65 respondents or 65% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.86 which was included in the strongly agree

criteria. Related with feeling confidence when ride Vespa, respondents gave an assessment of the VESPA brand statement making them more confident using it, indicating that most of them, namely 56 respondents or 56% stated strongly agree and obtained a total score of 3.78 which was included in the criteria for strongly agree.

Purchasing decision as a dependent variable in this study, it has also six indicators. Those indicators are better benefit than other motorcycle, knowing about Vespa make respondents wants to buy, watching the promotion make respondents evaluate the Vespa, good price, comfortable, and after sale service. Respondents' responses about having used other branded vehicles, but only the VESPA which was able to provide good driving benefits for consumers showed that most of them, as many as 53 respondents or 53% agreed, and obtained a total score of 3.63 who meet the criteria for agreeing. For respondents' responses regarding hearing/seeing product information VESPA allows you to make purchases at a certain time, it shows that most of the 65 respondents or 65% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.92 which was included in the strongly agreed criteria. Respondents' responses regarding hearing/seeing promotions or information on the VESPA product, allowing respondents to evaluate the product, showed that most of them, namely 53 respondents or 53% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.71 which was included in the agree criteria.

Respondents' responses regarding the price is a reasonable price for me to make a purchase with the desired benefits. It shows that most of them, namely 53 respondents or 53% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.73 which fall into the agreed criteria. Respondents' responses regarding after making a purchase felt that the VESPA met the desired driving comfort, mostly 61 respondents or 61% stated strongly agree and obtained a total score of 3.62 which was included in the agreed criteria. Respondents' responses regarding after the respondent made a purchase of the VESPA product, it was possible to recommend it to others, it showed that most of the 52 respondents or 52% agreed and obtained a total score of 3.62 which was included in the agreed criteria. These results show that so far, after purchasing the VESPA product, respondents have made it possible to recommend it to others.

C. Classical Assumptions

Classical assumptions that used in this study are normality test, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test. First classical assumption that used in this study is normality test. In this study, the data normality test used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov sample test method with a normal distribution test where the criteria used were: if Sig > 5% (α

= 0.05), the research data came from a normally distributed population. The results of the normality test of the data obtained the value of sig. of 0.406. Therefore, the data used in this study is normally distributed. The second classical assumption is multicollinearity test. Multicollinearity is to test whether the regression model found a correlation between independent variables. If there is a correlation, it is called a multicollinearity problem. Multicollinearity detection is based on the amount of VIF (Variance Inflating Factor) and tolerance. The results of the multicollinearity test show that the VIF value of each independent variable is around one and the tolerance value is close to 1 (1.056 for promotion, 1.026 for brand image). Based on these results, it can be concluded that the regression model used is free of multicollinearity. The third classical assumption is heteroscedasticity. The heteroscedasticity test is to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance from the residuals from one observation to another. If the variance of the residual from one observation to another observation remains, it is called homoscedasticity. On the other hand, if the variances are different, it is called heteroscedasticity. A good regression model is that there is no heteroscedasticity. Detection of the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model can be seen from the pattern formed at the points contained in the scatterplot graph. If there is a clear pattern and points that expand above and below zero on the Y axis, then there is no heteroscedasticity. Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, it is known that the points formed on the scatterplot graph do not form a clear pattern, and are spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, so it can be concluded that the regression model used is free of heteroscedasticity.

D. Result of Multiple Linear Regression

In this section, statistical results are presented regarding the effect of promotion and brand image on purchasing decisions of the VESPA. Data have been processed by the computer through the SPSS program with partial and simultaneous multiple linear regression analysis. Table 1 below shows the recapitulation of multiple regression analysis results.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.744	1.347		2.038	.044
Promotion	.164	.065	.171	2.539	.013
Brand Image	.693	.064	.734	10.909	.000

Table 1: Recapitulation of Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2022

• Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decision

Multiple linear regression calculation to predict the magnitude of the dependent variable on the independent variable. The regression equation used is as follows:

$$Y = 2,744 + 0,164 X_1 + 0,693X_2$$

Based on Table 1, partially each independent variable has an effect on purchasing decisions for VESPA. $a = 2.744$ is a constant value, means that the estimated purchase decision of VESPA, if the independent variables, namely promotion and brand image, have a value equal to zero. $b_1 = 0.164$ is the slope or direction coefficient of the promotion

variable (X_1) that affects the purchasing decision of the VESPA (Y), meaning that the promotion variable has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of the VESPA, if other variables are held constant. This means that with increasing promotional activities, purchasing decisions for VESPA will increase. $b_2 = 0.693$ is the slope or direction coefficient of the brand image variable (X_2) which affects the purchasing decision of the VESPA (Y), meaning that the brand image variable has a positive effect on the purchasing decision of the VESPA, if other variables are considered constant. This means that with the increasing brand image, the purchasing decision of the VESPA will increase.

Coefficient of Determination Value of this study can be seen in the table 2 below.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.848	.719	.713	1.307

Table 2: Coefficient of Determination Value

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2022

• Predictors: (Constant, Brand Image, Promotion

Based on table 2 above, the results of the calculation of the multiple linear regression analysis that has been carried out, it shows the ability of the model to explain the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is large, it can be seen in the value of Adjusted R. Square (R^2) that is equal to 0.713. It means that the regression model used is able to explain the effect of promotion and brand image variables on purchasing decisions of VESPA by 71.3%, while the remaining 28.7% is explained by other variables not included in this study.

To determine the effect of each independent variable, namely the promotion and brand image partially influence the purchasing decision of the VESPA this study used the t-test by comparing the t-count with t-table. The t-table at an alpha of 5% can be obtained a number of 1.984 at a 5%

significance level ($=0.05$). The result of significance also can be seen in the table 1. Based on the statistical results that shown in the table 1, the effect of the promotion variable (X_1) on the purchasing decision of the VESPA (Y), the t-count is 2.539, because the t-count > t-table ($2.539 > 1.984$), it is concluded that partially the promotion variable (X_1) has a significant effect on purchasing decisions for VESPA. The influence of the brand image variable (X_2) on the purchasing decision of VESPA (Y), the t-count is 10.909, because the t-count > t-table ($10.909 < 1.984$) it can be concluded that partially the brand image variable (X_2) has a significant effect on purchasing decisions for VESPA.

To find out whether the independent variables simultaneously have an influence on the dependent variable or have no effect, the F-test is used, by comparing F-count and F-Table at a significant level of 5% ($=0.05$). Result of F-test can be seen in the table 3 below.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	423.894	2	211.947	123.986	.000
	Residual	165.816	97	1.709		
	Total	589.710	99			

Table 3: Result of F-test

Source: Primary Data Processed, Year 2022

• Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decision

• Predictors: (Constant), Brand Image, Promotion

Based on the table 3 above, $Df_1 = 2$ and $Df_2 = 97$ at an alpha of 5%, the F- table is 3.090 while the F-count is 123.986 so that from the above calculations it can be seen that $F\text{-count} > F\text{-table}$, so it can be said that the promotion and brand image variables simultaneously influence the purchasing decision of the VESPA (Y).

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The results of the analysis can be seen that there is a significant influence between promotions on purchasing decisions for VESPA motorcycle products, meaning that with increasing promotional activities carried out, purchasing decisions will increase. The existence of this influence indicates that the respondents stated that the promotional activities carried out by the company in this case the advertisement for the VESPA product in mass

media such as television, radio, and the internet were in accordance with reality. In addition, with consumers having received notifications about the VESPA product in the form of emails and leaflets and others, the sales promotion of the VESPA was carried out massively and in large, clear information about the VESPA which is conveyed through internet media, the promotion of VESPA is increasingly convincing that the product is useful and the VESPA promotion is very creative, making consumer decisions increase. The results of this study support the results of previous research conducted by Cahyono (2018) which showed that promotion has a significant influence on purchasing decisions.

The results of the analysis can be seen that there is a significant influence between brand images on purchasing decisions for motorcycles with the VESPA brand, meaning that the better the brand image, the purchasing decisions will increase. The significant influence also shows that with an increase in brand image in this case regarding having heard/seen if the VESPA has a unique and futuristic design, the VESPA is a brand that is easy to remember and have heard/seen if VESPA has agile handling and is comfortable to drive. A good brand image is also shown by the VESPA is a big and well-known brand, the VESPA has a more attractive design than other similar motorcycles and the VESPA brand makes it more confident to use it, purchasing decisions will increase. According to Aaker (2010) brand image is how customers and others perceive a brand. Brand image is the result of consumer views or research on a good or bad brand. The results of this study support previous research conducted by Cahyono (2018), which showed that brand image has a significant influence on purchasing decisions.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of this study show that promotion and brand image are proven to have a significant influence on purchasing decisions both partially and simultaneously. This means that with changes in promotional activities and brand image, purchasing decisions will change. Brand image is an impression, feeling or conception that exists in the public about a company, about an object, person or about an institution. From this understanding, the company must be able to create an attractive brand, easy to remember, and describe the benefits of the product in accordance with the wishes and needs of consumers. Customer perception of a good brand image can be considered by consumers in making purchases. The consumer's view of a product is closely related to the quality of the product itself, where quality is one of the factors that a consumer considers before deciding to buy a product.

Promotion as a marketing mix strategy is very important in relation to the success of a product, where people who act as customers need information about a product before deciding to buy it. Promotional strategies are a means of communication between sellers and buyers to convey the benefits and uses of a product. It is expected that from the promotion of consumers can get to know the company's products.

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